

Synthesis of some new 2-substituted quinazoline derivatives

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Manuscript received 17 February 2009, revised 08 July 2010, accepted 20 July 2010

Abstract : 2-(2'-Amino-4'-methylpyrimidine-5-yl sulfanyl)-3-arylquinazolin-4(3H)ones (**4**) have been obtained by reaction of compound **3** with guanidine. Condensation of hydrazino derivatives (**6**) with variously substituted aryl aldehydes gave 2-(arylidenehydrazinomethyloxyethylthio)-3-arylquinazolin-4(3H)ones (**7**). Further, 3-arylquinazolin-4(3H)one-2-yl-1-arylthiosemicarbazones (**10**) have been obtained from hydrazino derivatives (**9**).

Keywords : Quinazoline, synthesis, condensation, hydrazino derivatives.

Introduction

The quinazoline derivatives have been reported to possess significant biological and pharmacological activities¹⁻³ especially anti-inflammatory⁴, anti-allergic⁵, analgesic⁶, CNS depressant⁷, antimicrobial⁸, hypnotic⁹, anti-convulsant¹⁰, antibacterial¹¹, anti-HIV¹², antihypertensive¹³, anthelmintic¹⁴, antitubercular¹⁵, insecticidal¹⁶ etc. In the present paper, we reported the synthesis of some new 2-substituted quinazoline derivatives.

The treatment of anthranilic acid with thiocarbamate salts of substituted anilines and carbon disulfide gave substituted 2-thio-3-arylquinazolin-4(3H)one (**1**).

Compounds **1** were *S*-alkylated with chloroacetone and chloroacetyl chloride to form 2-(propanonylsulfanyl)-3-arylquinazolin-4(3H)one (**2**) and 2-(chloroacetylthio)-3-arylquinazolin-4(3H)one (**5**) respectively. The treatment of **2** with DMF-DMA gave intermediate compound **3** which on further reaction with guanidine to form 2-(2'-amino-4'-methylpyrimidinesulfanyl)-3-arylquinazolin-4(3H)one (**4**). Further the compound **5** on reaction with hydrazine hydrate gave hydrazino derivatives (**6**) which on condensation with variously substituted aryl aldehydes formed the corresponding hydrazones (**7**). Compound **1** on treatment with cyanogen bromide gave 2-(isothiocyanato)-3-arylquinazolin-4(3H)one (**8**). The condensation of **4** with hydrazine hydrate yielded hydrazino de-

rivative (**9**) which on further condensation with variously substituted aldehydes gave the corresponding hydrazones (**10**).

Results and discussion

The treatment of **1a** with chloroacetone and chloroacetyl chloride in acetone in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate gave *S*-alkylated compounds **2a** and **5a** respectively. The formation of compound **2a** has been explained by the appearance of three singlets appeared at δ 2.3, 3.4 and 3.9 due to the $-\text{COCH}_3$, $-\text{OCH}_3$ and $\text{S}-\text{CH}_2$ in its ¹H NMR spectrum and the observation of the additional IR band at 1715 cm^{-1} . Similarly, the formation of compound **5a** was ascertained by the appearance of additional singlets at δ 4.1 in ¹H NMR due to $-\text{COCH}_2\text{-Cl}$ and IR band at 1725 cm^{-1} . Compound **2a** when reacted with DMF-DMA in methanol gave the compound **3a**. The appearance of two singlets at δ 9.1 and 3.15 due to $=\text{CH}$ and $-\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$ and disappearance of a singlet due to $\text{S}-\text{CH}_2$ at δ 3.9 in the spectrum indicates its formation. The compound **3a** on cyclisation with guanidine sulphate in alcoholic NaOH gave the compound **4a**. The formation of compound **4a** has been established on the basis of the disappearance of IR band due to acyclic $\text{C}=\text{O}$ observed at 1710 cm^{-1} in compound **3a** and $-\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$ protons in its ¹H NMR spectrum. The compound **5a** on reaction with hydrazine hydrate gave hydrazino derivative (**6a**).

The formation of **6a** was confirmed by the appearance of band at 3380–3200 cm^{-1} due to NHNH_2 . The condensation of **6a** with substituted aryl aldehydes gave the corresponding arylidene derivative (**7**). The disappearance of broad signal encountered at δ 6.1 due to NH_2 in ^1H NMR of **6** and the appearance of ^1H NMR signal due to $=\text{CH}$ at δ 8.9 indicated the formation of **7**.

Compound **1c** on treatment with cyanogen bromide in alcoholic NaOH gave compound **8c**. The appearance of IR band at 1640–1630 cm^{-1} due to $\text{N}=\text{C}=\text{S}$ indicates its formation. The compound **8c** on reaction with hydrazine hydrate gave the compound **9c**, the structure of which has been established by observing the additional IR band at 3350–3150 cm^{-1} due to NHNH_2 . The compound **9** on condensation with substituted aryl aldehydes yielded the corresponding compound **10** confirmed by their IR and ^1H NMR spectral data (Scheme 1).

Experimental

All ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker A-300 F-NMR spectrometer. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer. All chemicals used were of AR grade and are used without further purification. Melting points were determined by open capillary method, and are uncorrected. Purity of the products was checked by TLC.

The starting compounds **1a-c** were prepared by reported method¹⁷.

2-(2'-Propanonylsulfanyl)-3-(*o*-methylphenyl)quinazoline-4(3H)one (**2a**) :

The compound **1a** (2.84 g, 0.01 mol) and chloroacetone (0.93 g, 0.01 mol) was dissolved in dry acetone (10 ml), to which anhydrous potassium carbonate was added and reaction mixture refluxed for 18 h, cooled and separated solid was extracted with ether. After removal of ether under reduced pressure gave solid, which was recrystallised from ethanol to furnish (**2a**); yield 70%; m.p. 100 °C (Found : C, 63.45; H, 4.67; N, 8.29. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2\text{S}$ requires : C, 63.51; H, 4.74; N, 8.23%); IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 1715 (C=O), 1680 (cyclic amide C=O); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 2.3 (3H, s, $-\text{COCH}_3$), 3.4 (3H, s, Ar-OCH₃), 3.9 (2H, s, S-CH₂), 7.2–8.1 (8H, m, ArH) ppm; Mass (m/z) : 340 (M^+), 309, 297, 283, 251, 233

(100%), 107, 89; (m.p. °C, yield %); **2b**, 145, 80; **2c**, 195, 72.

4-Dimethylamino-3-(3-arylquinazolin-4(3H)only-2-sulfanyl)but-3-en-2-one (**3a**) :

The mixture of **2a** (1.7 g, 0.005 mol), dimethylformamide dimethylacetal (0.675 g, 0.005 mol) in methanol (5 ml) was stirred for ½ h and refluxed further on water bath at 70 °C for 2 h, cooled, concentrated and separated solid was recrystallised from ethanol; yield, 69%; m.p. 173 °C (Found : C, 63.87; H, 5.40; N, 10.53. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_3\text{N}_3\text{S}$ requires : C, 63.78; H, 5.35; N, 10.62%); IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 1712 (C=O), 1680 (cyclic amide C=O); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 2.2 (3H, s, COCH_3), 3.3 (3H, s, Ar-OCH₃), 3.15 (6H, s, $-\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 9.1 (1H, s, =CH) ppm; Mass (m/z) : 395 (M^+), 364, 352, 351, 288 (100%), 251, 144, 107; (m.p. °C, yield %); **3b**, 179, 65; **3c**, 203, 69.

2-Amino-4-methyl-5-(3-arylquinazolin-4(3H)only-2-sulfanyl)pyrimidine (**4a**) :

To the mixture of compound **3a** (0.395 g, 0.001 mol) and guanidine (0.06 g, 0.001 mmol) in methanol (5 ml), 2 N NaOH (2 ml) was added drop wise during 1 h with constant stirring. The same mixture was refluxed further for 5 h on a water bath and solvent removed under vacuum. The residue was dissolved in 5 ml H_2O , precipitated with 30% acetic acid, filtered, recrystallised from ethanol; yield, 62%; m.p. 205 °C (Found : C, 61.29; H, 4.30; N, 17.81. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_2\text{N}_5\text{S}$ requires : C, 61.37; H, 4.38; N, 17.89%); IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 1685 (cyclic amide C=O), 3350–3100 (NH_2); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 2.1 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 3.4 (3H, s, Ar-OCH₃), 7.0–8.1 (9H, m, ArH), 9.3 (2H, s, exchangeable with D_2O , NH_2) ppm; Mass (m/z) : 391 (M^+), 360, 284 (100%), 251, 140, 108, 107; (m.p. °C, yield %); **4b**, 165, 68; **4c**, 210, 71.

2-Chloroacetylthio-3-arylquinazolin-4(3H)one (**5a**) :

To the cold solution of compound **1a** (2.84 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone (10 ml) and anhydrous potassium carbonate, chloroacetyl chloride (1.130 g, 0.01 mol) was added drop wise with stirring and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 10 h, cooled, concentrated and the separated solid was extracted with ether. Excess ether was removed under vacuum to get a solid which was recrystallized from

Note

R, a = *p*-OCH₃

b = *p*-CH₃

c = *p*-Br

Scheme

ethanol to furnish compound 5a; yield, 75%; m.p. 145 °C (Found : C, 56.66; H, 3.54; N, 7.80. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2\text{SCl}$ requires : C, 56.59; H, 3.63; N, 7.76%); IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 1725 (C=O), 1685 (cyclic amide C=O); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 3.2 (3H, s, Ar-OCH₃), 4.1 (2H, s, -COCH₂-Cl), 7.0–8.2 (8H, m, ArH); Mass (m/z) : 360 (M^+), 329, 325, 311, 283, 253 (100%), 251, 109, 107, 77; (m.p. °C, yield %); 5b, 145, 80; 5c, 156, 81.

2-(Hydrazinomethyloxy)-3-arylquinazolin-4(3H)one (6a) :

The solution of compound 5a (1.082 g, 0.003 mol) in ethanol (15 ml), hydrazine hydrate (0.150 g, 0.003 mol) was added drop wise with stirring during 15 min. The separated solid was filtered and recrystallized from ethanol; yield, 80%; m.p. 207 °C (Found : C, 57.21; H, 4.44; N, 15.64. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3\text{N}_4\text{S}$ requires : C, 57.29; H,

4.53; N, 15.72%); IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 1712 (C=O), 1685 (cyclic amide C=O), 3380–3200 (NHNH₂); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ 3.4 (3H, s, Ar-OCH₃), 3.8 (2H, s, COCH₂), 6.1 (2H, s, -NH₂), 7.0–8.1 (8H, m, ArH), 9.8 (1H, s, -NH) ppm; Mass (*m/z*): 356 (M⁺), 325, 311, 283, 251, 249 (100%), 107, 105, 73, 45; (m.p. °C, yield %); **6b**, 210, 65; **6c**, 211, 69.

2-(Arylidenehydrazinomethyloxo)-3-arylquinazolin-4(3H)one (7_{a-1}) :

To the mixture of equimolar quantities of **6a** (0.356 g, 0.004 mol), salicylaldehyde (0.122 g, 0.004 mol) in methanol (10 ml) and 2–3 drops of acetic acid was added and reaction mixture heated on steam bath for 15 min. The separated solid was filtered and recrystallized from ethanol; yield, 69%; m.p. 263 °C (Found : C, 62.57; H, 4.29; N, 12.09. C₂₄H₂₀O₄N₄S requires : C, 62.60; H, 4.38; N, 12.17%); IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 1715 (C=O), 1680 (cyclic amide C=O); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ 3.5 (3H, s, Ar-OCH₃), 3.9 (2H, s, -CH₂), 6.9–8.1 (13H, m, Ar-H and -NH-), 8.9 (1H, s, =CH), 11.4 (1H, s, OH) ppm; Mass (*m/z*): 460 (M⁺), 429, 367, 354, 353 (100%), 340, 325, 311, 251, 135, 107, 93; (R', m.p. °C, yield %); **7_{a-2}**, *p*-OCH₃C₆H₄, 250, 76; **7_{a-3}**, *o*-ClC₆H₄, 260, 62; **7_{a-4}**, *p*-ClC₆H₄, 261, 72; **7_{a-5}**, *m*-OHC₆H₄, 260, 70; **7_{a-6}**, *o*-OHC₆H₄, 264, 71; **7_{a-7}**, *o*-NO₂C₆H₄, 270, 81; **7_{a-8}**, *o*-OH, *m*-OCH₃C₆H₃, 230, 59; **7_{a-9}**, *p*-N(CH₃)₂C₆H₄, 255, 73; **7_{a-10}**, 2,3,4-(CH₃)₃C₆H₃, 225, 56; **7_{b-1}**, *p*-OHC₆H₄, 245, 63; **7_{b-2}**, *p*-OCH₃C₆H₄, 255, 72; **7_{b-3}**, *o*-ClC₆H₄, 235, 66; **7_{b-4}**, *p*-ClC₆H₄, 253, 71; **7_{b-5}**, *m*-OHC₆H₄, 270, 59; **7_{b-6}**, *o*-OHC₆H₄, 236, 68; **7_{b-7}**, *o*-NO₂C₆H₄, 275, 72; **7_{b-8}**, *o*-OH, *m*-OCH₃C₆H₃, 235, 70; **7_{b-9}**, *p*-N(CH₃)₂C₆H₄, 265, 79; **7_{b-10}**, 2,3,4-(CH₃)₃C₆H₃, 260, 68; **7_{c-1}**, *p*-OHC₆H₄, 255, 59; **7_{c-2}**, *p*-OCH₃C₆H₄, 272, 71; **7_{c-3}**, *o*-ClC₆H₄, 278, 69; **7_{c-4}**, *p*-ClC₆H₄, 252, 67; **7_{c-5}**, *m*-OHC₆H₄, 274, 61; **7_{c-6}**, *o*-OHC₆H₄, 278, 58; **7_{c-7}**, *o*-NO₂C₆H₄, 254, 67; **7_{c-8}**, *o*-OH, *m*-OCH₃C₆H₃, 263, 79; **7_{c-9}**, *p*-N(CH₃)₂C₆H₄, 271, 72; **7_{c-10}**, 2,3,4-(CH₃)₃C₆H₃, 247, 68.

2-Isothiocyano-3-arylquinazolin-4(3H)one (8c) :

The solution of compound **1c** (1.67 g, 0.005 mol) in 10% methanolic NaOH (20 ml), cyanogen bromide (0.530 gm, 0.005 mol) was added and reaction mixture stirred for 30 min. The product obtained was filtered, washed

with water and recrystallized from 70% ethanol; yield, 72%; m.p. 162 °C (Found : C, 50.23; H, 2.31; N, 11.81. C₁₅H₈ON₃SBr requires : C, 50.30; H, 2.25; N, 11.73%); IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 1680 (cyclic amide C=O), 1640–1630 (N=C=S), 1620 (C=N); ¹H NMR : δ 6.8–7.5 (8H, m, ArH) ppm; Mass (*m/z*): 357 (M⁺), 325, 313, 299, 278, 202 (100%), 155; (m.p. °C, yield %); **8a**, 165, 75; **8b**, 171, 59.

4-(3-Arylquinazolin-4(3H)one-2-yl)semicarbazide (9c) :

The mixture of compound **8c** (0.72 g, 0.002 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.100 g, 0.002 mol) was heated in ethanol (15 ml) on a steam bath for 3 h, cooled and separated solid was filtered, and recrystallized from ethanol to furnish compound **9c**; yield, 80%; m.p. 208 °C (Found : C, 46.11; H, 2.92; N, 17.87. C₁₅H₁₂ON₅SBr requires : C, 46.2; H, 3.1; N, 17.9%); IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3350–3150 (-NHNH₂), 1680 (C=O), 1620 (C=S); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆): δ 5.9 (2H, s, -NH₂), 9.3 (2H, s, 2 × NH), 6.9–7.5 (8H, m, Ar-H) ppm; Mass (*m/z*): 389 (M⁺), 358, 314, 310, 299, 234 (100%), 155, 90; (m.p. °C, yield %); **9a**, 164, 67; **9b**, 179, 58.

3-Arylquinazolin-4(3H)one-2-yl-1-arylthiosemicarbazone (10_{a-1}) :

To the mixture of compound **9a** (0.17 g, 0.0005 mol) and *p*-methoxybenzaldehyde (0.068 g, 0.0005 mol) in ethanol (10 ml), 2–3 drops of acetic acid were added and the reaction mixture was refluxed on a steam bath for 2.5 h. The separated solid was filtered, and recrystallized from ethanol; yield, 61%; m.p. 272 °C (Found : C, 64.91, H, 4.48; N, 12.68. C₂₄H₂₀O₃N₄S requires : C, 64.85; H, 4.54; N, 12.60%); IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 1680 (cyclic amide C=O), 1620 (C=S), 1615 (C=N); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆): δ 3.6 (3H, s, Ar-OCH₃), 3.9 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 7.0–8.2 (12H, m, Ar-H), 8.4 (2H, bs, 2 × NH), 8.7 (1H, s, =CH) ppm; Mass (*m/z*): 444 (M⁺), 427, 413, 351, 337 (100%), 309, 251, 193, 135, 107, 93; (R', m.p. °C, yield %); **10_{a-2}**, *p*-OCH₃C₆H₄, 267, 69; **10_{a-3}**, *o*-ClC₆H₄, 249, 62; **10_{a-4}**, *p*-ClC₆H₄, 261, 67; **10_{a-5}**, *m*-OHC₆H₄, 269, 71; **10_{a-6}**, *o*-OHC₆H₄, 246, 60; **10_{a-7}**, *o*-NO₂C₆H₄, 257, 77; **10_{a-8}**, *o*-OH, *m*-OCH₃C₆H₃, 246, 63; **10_{a-9}**, *p*-N(CH₃)₂C₆H₄, 267, 71; **10_{a-10}**, 2,3,4-(CH₃)₃C₆H₃, 266, 67; **10_{b-1}**, *p*-OHC₆H₄, 272, 58; **10_{b-2}**, *p*-OCH₃C₆H₄, 257,

80; **10_{b-3}**, *o*-ClC₆H₄, 267, 71; **10_{b-4}**, *p*-ClC₆H₄, 245, 66; **10_{b-5}**, *m*-OHC₆H₄, 258, 70; **10_{b-6}**, *o*-OHC₆H₄, 264, 64; **10_{b-7}**, *o*-NO₂C₆H₄, 243, 69; **10_{b-8}**, *o*-OH, *m*-OCH₃C₆H₃, 264, 71; **10_{b-9}**, *p*-N(CH₃)₂C₆H₄, 254, 63; **10_{b-10}**, 2,3,4-(CH₃)₃C₆H₃, 265, 65; **10_{c-1}**, *p*-OHC₆H₄, 269, 68; **10_{c-2}**, *p*-OCH₃C₆H₄, 257, 64; **10_{c-3}**, *o*-ClC₆H₄, 261, 70; **10_{c-4}**, *p*-ClC₆H₄, 257, 67; **10_{c-5}**, *m*-OHC₆H₄, 267, 62; **10_{c-6}**, *o*-OHC₆H₄, 248, 58; **10_{c-7}**, *o*-NO₂C₆H₄, 257, 72; **10_{c-8}**, *o*-OH, *m*-OCH₃C₆H₃, 268, 75; **10_{c-9}**, *p*-N(CH₃)₂C₆H₄, 257, 68; **10_{c-10}**, 2,3,4-(CH₃)₃C₆H₃, 262, 78.

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